

FACTORS IN THE MANIFESTATION OF MENTAL HEALTH DURING ADOLESCENCE

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Annotation: This article highlights the psychological characteristics of adolescence and their manifestations, as well as the fact that the level and quality of psychological health depends on the level of social, socio-psychological and individual-mental adaptation indicators of the individual.

Key words: *Mental health, psychological characteristics, stress, depression, loneliness, cognitive problems, cognitive processes, quality of psychological health, individual-mental adaptation*

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in attention to psychological health issues. Attention to the health of school children has naturally increased. The concept of health technology, which has emerged in recent years, involves combining all the efforts of school students to maintain, shape and strengthen their health. The task of school teachers is to fully prepare the teenager for independent living, to create all the conditions for his happy development. And without health, this cannot be achieved. Therefore, the school lays the foundation for the well-being of future generations by ensuring the health of schoolchildren and shaping their own health culture.

There are more than 300 recipes for "health". We distinguish the main groups in which health is defined: • as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, rather than the absence of disease or physical disabilities; • The body as a set of physical and mental abilities (vitality) that have a personality; • As an integral multidimensional dynamic state in the process of realizing genetic potential in a particular social and economic environment, allowing man to perform his biological and social functions at different levels. Thus, the understanding of health is different, but in each definition the psychological (spiritual) health of an individual is mentioned as an important link in the understanding of health. One of the most damaging factors influencing the deterioration of the health of school children is the general stressful system by which many teachers organize the learning process and conduct lessons. Up to 80% of students experience constant educational stress. Thus, rapidly deteriorating

indicators of neuropsychological and psychological health. The term “mental health” is not yet frequently used. However, if a person cannot be called either healthy or sick, it is advisable to use the term “psychological health” to assess the state of health.

The level and quality of psychological health is characterized by indicators of social, socio-psychological and individual-mental adaptation of the individual. Health psychology focuses on a healthy person, his individual psychological characteristics, the sources of his psyche, which allows him to maintain his health when the pathogenic factors of the environment are inevitable. For school students, such a pathogenic factor is school stress as a state of psycho-emotional stress of varying duration, which is accompanied by a feeling of discomfort. An important feature of emotional stress is increased anxiety. The main task of aggression in this case is to protect from the outside world, it is dangerous for the child. Therefore, such children have a fear of death in one form or another, which they usually deny.

In the passive version, he develops a fear of self-expression. The child behaves, refuses to talk to adults about their problems. As a rule, after a while, changes in the body are felt: rigidity of movements, monotony of sound, avoidance of eye contact. The child is in a protective mask. If the origin of the problems is preschool age, the child usually clearly feels inferior. In this case, in the active version, he tries to compensate for this feeling by showing aggression towards those who are weaker than himself. They can be peers, sometimes even parents and teachers. Often aggression manifests itself in the form of ridicule, harassment, use of insulting words. At the same time, insulting another person is of particular interest, and the negative attitude of others enhances the child’s motivation for these actions, as it serves as proof of his or her usefulness. It can be assumed that compensatory aggression underlies many forms of antisocial behavior.

Feeling inferior in the passive version takes the form of fear of growth when the adolescent avoids making his or her own decisions, displays infantile position and social maturity. Psychological health disorders are associated with the complication of the normative crisis of adolescence, which originates during adolescence and is commonly referred to as the crisis of identity. In this case, the adolescent experiences a sense of anxiety because he or she is unable to feel the integrity of his or her “I”. Then, when there is an active position, and at this age, usually the teenager resists any social influences: he refuses to study, to follow discipline in the classroom, to go to a psychologist. He wears a “I’m fine” protective mask, hiding a deep sense of anxiety from himself in the first place. In the most difficult situations, teenagers completely lose their focus

on the future and live one day. In the passive version, the norms and rules are followed from the outside, the fear of self-determination, not thinking about choosing a family and a professional role, the desire to "stick" to the parents, as well as the rejection of the future fear of existing and independent decision making. When under stress and at risk of death, the human body does not have time to process information normally through the cerebral cortex, and then simpler and simpler instinctive mechanisms of behavior controlled by subcortical regions are activated in the brain (subcortex of the brain), performs endocrine regulation and management of emotional reactions and states.

In other words, in extreme and stressful situations, from a physiological point of view, the information is transmitted directly through the amygdala through the thalamus, bypassing the cerebral cortex from the outside. A small almond-shaped lead in the subcortex of the brain, the amygdala, which is responsible for fear reactions, automatically activates a self-defense mechanism that allows the human body to enter a self-defense mode without even having time to think. About the danger that threatens him. This mechanism can be defined by the phrase "fight or fly" (fight or fly), which is well known in psychology. This reaction of the human body to danger is normal and protective. A painful condition can occur if the body seems to be "fixing" on such a reaction and perceives any situation as stressful. The child loses a sense of security and integrity of his own body, as well as a sense of confidence in himself and those close to him. A person's perception of an event as traumatic is very individual and depends on his or her personality, the level of involvement in the event, and the experience of perceiving and overcoming dramatic situations.

Any difficult situation leads to disruption of activities, relationships are established, negative emotions and experiences are caused, cause discomfort. All of this, under certain conditions, can have negative consequences for an individual's development. Difficult situations under the influence of which behavioral patterns are formed and attitudes to difficulties are formed have a different character. These can be temporary, transient, everyday events for the child (they did not enter the game, fell off the bike, forgot the house key, etc.); short-term, but very important and acute situations (loss of a close relative, separation from a family member, a sudden change in life stereotypes); or, conversely, cases of long-lasting, chronic behavior, usually related to the family environment (parental divorce, conflicting or arbitrary upbringing, parental alcoholism, etc.); as well as situations that occur under the influence of emotional deprivation factors (hospitalization, day and night stay in children) (preschool education institutions, etc.). The greatest impacts on children are acute mental trauma and chronic psycho-traumatic effects, which are associated

with increased risk and poor adaptive reactions. Their influence on the formation of the child's personality is also not great. This can be explained by the need to overcome all the "trifles of life", to find a solution every time. It is in such everyday situations that the child gets a successful or unsuccessful experience of overcoming obstacles, determines his attitude to difficulties, "tries" different ways of action, develops the most optimal tactics of behavior.

I.A. Arshavsky points out that the body is not in a state of equilibrium or equilibrium with the environment during its development. Rather, it is an unbalanced system in which the organism constantly changes its interactions with environmental conditions during development. According to G.L. Apanasenko, if we look at man as a bioenergetic information system characterized by a pyramidal structure of subsystems containing the body, psyche and spiritual element, the concept of health means the harmony of this system. Disturbances of any degree affect the stability of the whole system. G.A. Kuraev, S.K.Sergeev and Yu.V.Slenov point out that many definitions of health are based on the human body's resistance, adaptation, overcoming, maintaining, expanding its capabilities, and so on. The authors argue that with a sense of health, man is seen as a militant being in an aggressive natural and social environment. However, the biological environment does not produce an organism that does not support it, and if this happens, then such an organism will collapse at the beginning of its development. Researchers suggest defining health based on the basic functions of the human body (genetic unconditioned reflex program, instinctive activity, innate and acquired functions). nervous activity). Accordingly, health can be defined as the ability of interactive body systems to implement genetic programs of unconditional reflexes, instincts, processes, generative functions, mental activity, and phenotypic behaviors toward social and cultural spheres of life. . One possible answer is as follows. Clinicians may determine that some mental illnesses can be better treated with medications and others with psychotherapy. These beliefs about the effectiveness of treatment can lead to beliefs about the causal basis of mental illness; drug-sensitive diseases are more biologically based, and disorders that respond to psychotherapy are considered more social. Of course, the causal direction may be the opposite; Physicians' beliefs about the root causes of mental illness can lead to their beliefs about the effectiveness of treatments. To look at health from a philosophical point of view, it must be understood that it reflects a necessity arising from the nature of events, and that disease is an accident that does not have a universal character. Thus, modern medicine deals mainly with accidental phenomena - diseases, not with health, it is natural and necessary. Another possibility is that two beliefs can reinforce each other.

Further research could investigate this issue in more depth using longitudinal observation or false distortions. Another, but more valuable way to explain negative correlation is to look at the specific causes of mental illness in which a negative correlation occurs.

In short, we can see that there is a lot of scientific work on mental health, and Russian psychologists have conducted effective scientific research in this area. F. Perls believes that mental health is related to the maturity of the individual, he sees man as a whole, he has the ability to meet his needs, constructive behavior, healthy flexibility and responsibility for himself. 'is manifested in the ability to assume. When it comes to health, we are accustomed to imagining it primarily in relation to the state of the human body and body when it is not sick, as well as some of the pain that occurs during illness. The term is interpreted primarily in relation to the activities of health workers. But because the body and the body, the mind and the intellect are directly related to man, psychology, the science that studies the laws and mysteries of the human psyche, is also related to him. There is a department of health psychology in the field of psychology, which views health primarily as a reflection of the human mind and thinking. This means that the health of each of us, which is as important as water and air, is the subject of research not only in medicine, but also in psychology. So what does psychology focus on when studying health in terms of human behavior, attitudes, and various psychological states? What are some aspects of our seemingly secretive psyche that make us feel healthy, healthy, and refreshed? What opportunities do we have to manage our wealth and health by managing it? Health psychology teaches each of us to manage our mental state, to keep it moderate by detecting changes in our consciousness in a timely manner, to adapt to changing conditions, to prevent it and to improve hygiene. It is becoming more and more bold in our lives as a science and a useful practice.

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